

The Quantum-gravity Corrections to Primordial Black Holes and Some their Cosmological Consequences

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This paper presents a continuation of a study of taking into account the quantum-gravity corrections (**qgcs**) for primordial black holes (**pbhs**) and of the corresponding inferences in cosmology. The first part is devoted to application of the above-mentioned **qgcs** in the de Sitter epoch to solution of the Dark Energy Problem. In the process the Dark Energy is understood as the vacuum energy the density of which is identical to the cosmological constant within constant factors. The explicit formula for the transformation of this density due to **qgcs** for **pbhs** with the Schwarzschild-de Sitter metric in the de Sitter space has been derived. The case of a dynamic cosmological term in this formalism has been considered. The second part of the work is devoted to studies of **qgcs** for **pbhs** during the radiation-dominant era. At first it has been demonstrated that the inclusion of these corrections shifts all the parameters in accordance with the formulae applicable to the de Sitter epoch. Then the accretion and evaporation processes in this pattern are studied for **pbhs**. It has been shown that, compared with a semiclassical consideration, in this case the accretion rate is lowering, whereas the evaporation rate is growing, i.e., in this pattern the evaporation processes are intensified.

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1. Introduction

This paper is a natural continuation of the author works devoted to primordial black holes [1]–[4]. However, in the previous works the author has studied the inferences of taking into account the quantum-gravity corrections (**qgcs**) for various cosmological parameters and processes as regards the primordial black holes in the de Sitter space of the very Early Universe. But in this paper the attention is concentrated at the radiation-dominant era.

In the last years numerous works have been devoted to the mechanisms associated with the formation and effects of primordial black holes. It is worth noting both interesting reviews on this topic [5] and important results concerning specific

problems [6]–[8]. These articles and other works in the field of primordial black holes motivated the present research. The primordial black holes (**pbhs**) [9]–[11] in the Early Universe are due to gravitational collapse of the high-density matter [12]. In [13]–[15] a sufficiently accurate estimate of the mass **pbhs** $M(t)$ formed during the period of time t since the Big Bang has been obtained. And for small times close to the Planckian time $t = t_p \approx 10^{-43}$ s, the mass of **pbhs** is close to the Planck mass $M(t) \approx 10^{-5}g \propto m_p$.

When quantum gravity [16] is considered within the Generalized Uncertainty Principle (**GUP**) [17]–[21], the arbitrary **pbh** due to the Hawking evaporation process is not completely evaporated, having the nonvanishing Planckian remnant. It is obvious that **qgcs** of such black holes are significant.

In [1]–[4] the author calls such (and in a wider

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sense all) black holes of small mass the **quantum pbhs** (or **qpbhs**), introduced in [22],[23], noting that the quantum-gravitational effects for these objects could be significant. But in the above-mentioned works the inferences of taking into account **qgcs** are considered only for **pbhs** in the very early epoch – de Sitter epoch.

The first section briefly presents the principal results from [1]–[4] which are important for the consideration.

In the second section consideration is given to the application of **qgcs** for **pbhs** in the de Sitter epoch to solving the Dark Energy Problem. The Dark Energy is understood as the vacuum energy the density of which is identical to the cosmological constant Λ within constant factors. The explicit formula for the transformation of Λ , due to **qgcs** for **pbh** of the mass M with the Schwarzschild-de Sitter metric in the de Sitter space, is given. Besides, the case of the dynamic cosmological term $\Lambda = \Lambda(t)$ and evaporating **pbh** is considered.

The third section is devoted to a study of **pbhs** during the radiation dominant era. It is shown that taking into account of **qgcs** in this consideration leads to shifting of all the parameters similar to the formulae for the de Sitter era. Then in this pattern the evaporation processes are studied too. It is pointed out that, compared with the semiclassical pattern, in this case the accretion rate is lowering, whereas the evaporation rate is growing, i.e., for such **pbhs** with regard to **qgcs**, the evaporation processes are intensified.

In conclusion the possibility to use the obtained results for other models of the Dark Energy is considered, specifically for the Quintessence and the Dark Matter Problem.

In what follows the normalization $c = \hbar = 1$ is used, for which we have $G = l_p^2$.

2. Cosmological parameters, quantum-gravity corrections to black hole physics and necessary formulae

We will use the results published in [1]–[4]. Let us consider the primordial black hole **pbh**, with the Schwarzschild-de Sitter (SdS) metric [24] and small mass M , in the Early Universe

$$ds^2 = -f(\tilde{r})dt^2 + \frac{d\tilde{r}^2}{f(\tilde{r})} + \tilde{r}^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (1)$$

where $f(\tilde{r}) = 1 - 2GM/\tilde{r} - \Lambda\tilde{r}^2/3 = 1 - 2GM/\tilde{r} - \tilde{r}^2/L^2$, $L = \sqrt{3/\Lambda} = H_0^{-1}$, M is the black hole mass, Λ is the cosmological constant, and $L = H_0^{-1}$ is the Hubble radius.

As shown in [1], for such black holes, because their mass M is small, the formulae known for Schwarzschild black holes may be used to a high accuracy. In particular, their event horizon radius takes the form

$$r_M = 2GM. \quad (2)$$

In [24] for inflationary scenario the metric (1) is conveniently described in terms of the conformal time η :

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left\{ -d\eta^2 + \left(1 + \frac{\mu^3 \eta^3}{r^3}\right)^{4/3} \times \left[\left(\frac{1 - \mu^3 \eta^3 / r^3}{1 + \mu^3 \eta^3 / r^3}\right)^2 dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mu = (GMH_0/2)^{1/3}$, H_0 is the de Sitter-Hubble parameter and scale factor, a is the conformal time function η :

$$a(\eta) = -1/(H_0\eta), \eta < 0, \quad (4)$$

where r satisfies the condition $r_0 < r < \infty$ and a value of $r_0 = -\mu\eta$ in the reference frame of (3) conforms to singularity of the back hole.

In virtue (2), μ may be given as

$$\mu = (r_M H_0 / 4)^{1/3}. \quad (5)$$

In his paper [1] the author has studied the case $\mu = const$ when a black hole is considered taking into account the quantum-gravity corrections (**qgcs**). Within the scope of the Generalized Uncertainty Principle (**GUP**) these **qgcs** are calculated as follows [17]

$$[X, P] = i\hbar \exp\left(\frac{\alpha^2 l_p^2}{\hbar^2} P^2\right),$$

$$(\delta X)(\delta P) \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \left\langle \exp\left(\frac{\alpha^2 l_p^2}{\hbar^2} P^2\right) \right\rangle. \quad (6)$$

Then for saturate (**GUP***), $(\delta P)^2 = \langle P^2 \rangle - \langle P \rangle^2$ and in virtue of formula (8) in [17]

$$(\delta X)(\delta P) = \frac{\hbar}{2} \exp\left(\frac{\alpha^2 L_{Pl}^2}{\hbar^2} \left((\delta P)^2 + \langle P \rangle^2\right)\right). \quad (7)$$

It is further assumed that the holds true **GUP, GUP*** i.e. (6),(7). As a result, there is a possibility for the existence of a Planck Schwarzschild black hole and, accordingly, of a Schwarzschild sphere (further referred to as "minimal"), with the minimal mass M_0 and the minimal radius r_{min} (formula (20) in [17]) that is a theoretical minimal length $r_{min} \doteq r_0$:

$$r_0 = l_{min} = (\delta X)_0 = \sqrt{\frac{e}{2}} \alpha l_p, \quad M_0 = \frac{\alpha \sqrt{e}}{2\sqrt{2}} m_p, \quad (8)$$

where in (6),(8) α is the model-dependent parameter on the order of 1, e is the base of natural logarithms, and $r_0 \propto l_p, M_0 \propto m_p$. By virtue of (6),(7) [17] for black hole temperature T_H taking into account **qgcs** we obtain

$$T_{H,q} = \frac{1}{8\pi MG} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{8\pi MG} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2 + \frac{5}{8e^2} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^4 + \frac{49}{48e^3} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^6 + \dots\right), \quad (9)$$

or

[17])

$$M_q = M \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right); \quad W(u) e^{W(u)} = u. \quad (11)$$

$$r_{M_q} = 2M_q G = r_M \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right)$$

$$= r_M \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right), \quad (10)$$

where M_q, r_{M_q} is the black hole mass M and its radius r_M taking into account **qgcs**, $W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)$ – value at the corresponding point of the Lambert W-function $W(u)$ satisfying the equation (formulae (1.5) in [25] and (9) in

$W(u)$ is the multifunction for complex variable $u = x + yi$. However, for real $u = x, -1/e \leq u < 0, W(u)$ is the single-valued continuous function having two branches denoted by $W_0(u)$ and $W_{-1}(u)$, and for real $u = x, u \geq 0$ there is only one branch $W_0(u)$ [25].

Obviously, the quantum-gravitational correction **qgcs** (10) presents a *deformation* (or more exactly, the *quantum deformation* of a classical black-holes theory from the viewpoint of the paper [26] with the deformation parameter

M_0^2/M^2 :

$$\frac{M_0^2}{M^2} = \frac{r_0^2}{r_M^2} = \frac{l_{min}^2}{r_M^2}, \quad (12)$$

where $r_0 = l_{min}$ is the horizon radius of minimal **pbh** from formula (8).

It should be noted that this deformation parameter

$$l_{min}^2/r_M^2 \doteq \alpha_{r_M} \quad (13)$$

has been introduced by the author in his earlier works [27]–[32], where he studied deformation of quantum mechanics at Planck scales in terms of the deformed quantum mechanical density matrix.

As seen, $W(0) = 0$ is an obvious solution for the equation (11). For black hole with great mass $M \gg m_p$ we have

$$\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right) \approx 1. \quad (14)$$

and therefore for such black holes necessitates no consideration of **qgcs**. But in the case of small black holes we have

$$\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right) > 1. \quad (15)$$

It should be noted that, with the expansion $\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right)$ in terms of the small parameter $\alpha_{r_M} = (r_0/r_M)^2$, in formula (9) one can easily obtain the small-parameter expansion of the inverse number $\exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right)$, and also of all the integer powers for this exponent, specifically for its square $\exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{r_0}{r_M}\right)^2\right)\right)$.

In [24] it was assumed that $\mu = const$ (5) In [1] formula (5) was supplemented as follows

$$\mu = const = (r_M H_0/4)^{1/3} = (r_{M_q} H_{0,q}/4)^{1/3}, \quad (16)$$

where $H_{0,q}$ is the value of H_0 with due regard for the above **qgcs**. Now, from [1] we have

$$\begin{aligned} H_{0,q} &= H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right) \\ &= H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Then **qgc** for the scale factor $a(\eta)$ (4)

$$\begin{aligned} a(\eta) \rightarrow a(\eta)_q &\doteq -1/(H_{0,q}\eta) = -1 \left/ \left(H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right) \eta \right) \right. \\ &= -1 \left/ \left(H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \eta \right) \right. = a(\eta) \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \eta < 0, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

and for the Hubble parameter in general case $H(\eta) \doteq H$

$$H = a'(\eta)/a^2(\eta) \mapsto H_q(\eta) = a'(\eta)_q/a^2(\eta)_q \quad (19)$$

As directly follows from the last formula, in this pattern H_0 and H are identically transformed, i.e.

we have

$$H \mapsto H_q = H \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \quad (20)$$

Definition 2.1

Let us call the above-defined deformation M_q -**deformation** the *quantum deformation*

(formulae (12),(13)) due to **qgcs** for the Schwarzschild **qpbhs** of the mass M , calling the associated "shifts" of various quantities (for example, formulae (17)–(20),...)– M_q -**shifts**.

3. Some remarks on dark energy problem

As since the inflation potential energy $V(\phi_0) = \text{const}$ and [33]

$$H_0^2 = \frac{V(\phi_0)}{3m_p^2} \quad (21)$$

and the effective cosmological constant Λ :

$$\Lambda = \frac{V(\phi_0)}{m_p^2} = 3H_0^2. \quad (22)$$

Because, due to **qgcs** for the Schwarzschild **qpbhs** of the mass M , the quantity H_0 is transformed by formula (17), in this case the cosmological constant Λ is also subjected to the corresponding M_q -**deformation** (or M_q -**shifts**)

$$\Lambda \rightarrow \Lambda_q = \Lambda \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \quad (23)$$

According to the principal hypothesis, the dark energy density is the vacuum energy density satisfying the equation of state $p_\Lambda = -\rho_\Lambda$, where ρ_Λ is the negative initial pressure. As we have

$$\rho_\Lambda = \frac{\Lambda}{8\pi}, \quad (24)$$

the transformation (23) results in the M_q -deformed vacuum energy density ρ_{Λ_q} :

$$\rho_\Lambda \rightarrow \rho_{\Lambda_q} = \rho_\Lambda \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right). \quad (25)$$

Up to now it is assumed that the cosmological term Λ is constant.

Actually, due to the Bianchi identities [34]

$$\nabla_\mu G^\mu{}_\nu = 0, \quad (26)$$

where $G^\mu{}_\nu$ is the left hand side of the Einstein equations

$$G^\mu{}_\nu \equiv R^\mu{}_\nu - \frac{1}{2}\delta^\mu{}_\nu R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \left[T^\mu{}_\nu + \frac{c^4 \Lambda}{8\pi G} \delta^\mu{}_\nu \right], \quad (27)$$

the energy-momentum tensor $T^\mu{}_\nu$ (energy-momentum density tensor) remains covariantly valid

$$\nabla_\mu T^\mu{}_\nu = 0. \quad (28)$$

From whence it directly follows that the cosmological term Λ is a constant.

But, as has been rightly noted in several publications (e.g., [35]–[40]), conservation laws (28) are only regulating the energy-momentum exchange between the field sources and gravitational field and are liable to be violated if an independent energy source is existent in the Universe. Such a source may be associated with a time-varying cosmological term. In that case it is reasonable to consider $\Lambda = \Lambda(t)$.

Then the Bianchi identity (26) is replaced by the "generalized Bianchi identity" [38]

$$\nabla_\mu [T^\mu{}_\nu + \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu] = 0, \quad (29)$$

where $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu = \varepsilon_\Lambda \delta^\mu{}_\nu$ is some energy-momentum tensor (referred to as the dark energy-momentum tensor [38]) related to the cosmological term, where

$$\varepsilon_\Lambda = \frac{c^4 \Lambda}{8\pi G} \quad (30)$$

is the corresponding energy density.

It is clear that for long times and hence for large scales the effect of **qgcs** on the dynamic value $\Lambda(t)$ is negligible.

Consequently, without loss of generality, it is assumed that

$$\Lambda \approx \text{const}, t_\Lambda < t, \quad (31)$$

where t_Λ is the limiting point of the time scale, later than which the cosmological term may be

considered constant with a high accuracy. In this case the period $0 < t \leq t_\Lambda$ is short and within this period, when we take into account **qgcs** of **qpbh**, the transformation of Λ is performed according to (23).

But, according to the Hawking evaporation process, the initial **qpbh** at the period $0 < t \leq t_\Lambda$ loses its mass. When we take into account **qgcs**, a rate of the mass loss is of the form [17],[1]

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = -\frac{\gamma_1}{M^2 l_p^4} \exp\left(-2W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right) \times \left(1 - \frac{8\gamma_2}{e\gamma_1}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2 \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right)\right), \quad (32)$$

where $\gamma_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{480}$, $\gamma_2 = \frac{\pi^2}{16128}$.

The minus sign in the right side of the last formula

means that the black hole does not increase, but loses mass.

Due to (13), the formula (32) is of the following form:

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = -\frac{\gamma_1}{M^2 l_p^4} \exp(-2W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)) \times \left(1 - \frac{8\gamma_2}{e\gamma_1}\alpha_{r_M} \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right)\right). \quad (33)$$

We can expand the right sides of formulae (32) and (33) into a series in terms of the small parameter $e^{-1}(M_0/M)^2 = e^{-1}\alpha_{r_M}$ (the formula (46) in [17]) that, proceeding from the deformation parameter $\alpha_{r(M)}$, takes the form

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = -\frac{\gamma_1}{M^2 l_p^4} \left(1 + \frac{2}{e}\alpha_{r_M} + \frac{4}{e^2}\left(1 - \frac{2\gamma_2}{e\gamma_1}\right)\alpha_{r_M}^2 + \frac{25}{3e^3}\left(1 - \frac{72\gamma_2}{25e\gamma_1}\right)\alpha_{r_M}^3 + \dots\right). \quad (34)$$

Let t_M be a formation time of **qpbh** with the mass M , whereas the time \tilde{t} meets the condition $\tilde{t} : t_M < \tilde{t} \leq t_\Lambda$.

We can find a value of the mass loss of **qpbh** as a result of evaporation.

$$\Delta_{Evap,q}M(t_M, \tilde{t}) \doteq \int_{t_M}^{\tilde{t}} \frac{dM}{dt} = -\int_{t_M}^{\tilde{t}} \frac{\gamma_1}{M^2 l_p^4} \left(1 + \frac{2}{e}\alpha_{r_M} + \frac{4}{e^2}\left(1 - \frac{2\gamma_2}{e\gamma_1}\right)\alpha_{r_M}^2 + \frac{25}{3e^3}\left(1 - \frac{72\gamma_2}{25e\gamma_1}\right)\alpha_{r_M}^3 + \dots\right). \quad (35)$$

Next, we can determine the mass of a black hole after its evaporation until time \tilde{t} with regard to **qgcs**

$$M_{Evap,q}(t_M, \tilde{t}) \doteq M + \Delta_{Evap,q}M(t_M, \tilde{t}). \quad (36)$$

And similarly to the formula (10), we have

$$M_{Evap,q}(t_M, \tilde{t}) = M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t}) \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t})}\right)^2\right)\right), \quad (37)$$

where $M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t})$ – corresponding remnant after Hawking evaporation calculated during the same time interval $\tilde{t} - t_M$ within the scope of a semiclassical approximation.

Substituting the quantity $M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t})$ for M in all the above-mentioned formulae, we obtain the following:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{0,q} &= H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_{M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t})}}\right)\right), \\ \Lambda &\rightarrow \Lambda_q = \Lambda \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_{M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t})}}\right)\right), \\ \rho_\Lambda &\rightarrow \rho_{\Lambda_q} = \rho_\Lambda \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_{M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t})}}\right)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

As seen from the last formula, in this case a contribution made by **qgcs** for a primordial black hole into the vacuum energy density (dark energy) ρ_Λ is higher than in the initial one due to $M_{Evap}(t_M, \tilde{t}) < M$. From the above formulae it follows that black holes which are smaller in size make greater contributions into exponents of (38).

4. M_q -deformation in radiation-dominant epoch

4.1. General formalism

Let us consider taking into account **qgcs** for Schwarzschild **PBHs** in all scenarios, specifically during the radiation-dominant era [33]. Initially in this case **PBHs** are not **qbhs** but they become such in the process of evaporation. In this case it is necessary to take account of **qgcs**.

Then **qgcs** introduce changes into the corresponding formulae for this era, for example, see [41]. In particular, on the substitution of $M \rightarrow M_q, r \rightarrow r_{M_q}$ from (10) **qgcs**-corrections of the formulae (7)–(9) from [41], with due regard

for $c = \hbar = 1$, take the following form:

$$M_q = \frac{\gamma (m_p)^2}{2 H_{f,q}} \approx \gamma \frac{10^{10} \text{ GeV}}{H_{f,q}} 10^4 \text{ g} \gtrsim \frac{\gamma}{3} \text{ g}, \quad (39)$$

$$t_{f,q} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{M_q}{(m_p)^2} \quad (40)$$

$$k_B T_{f,q} = \left(\frac{45\gamma^2}{16\pi^3 g_*(T_f)}\right)^{1/4} \left(\frac{m_p}{M_q}\right)^{1/2} m_p. \quad (41)$$

where g denotes **gramms**, $H_{f,q}, t_{f,q}, T_{f,q}$ are **qgcs**-corrections of the Hubble parameter H_f and the cosmic time t_f at the formation of the PBH, $T_{f,q}$ is **qgc**-correction of the temperature T_f at the formation of the given PBH, $\gamma \lesssim 1$ is a numerical factor, $g_*(T_f) = \sum_B g_B + \frac{7}{8} \sum_F g_F$ and $g_{B(F)}$ is the number of degrees of freedom (dofs) for each boson (fermion) [41]. In our consideration it is connived that **qgcs**-corrections do not affect the number $g_{B(F)}$, i.e. $g_{B(F),q} \equiv g_{B(F)}$ and hence we have $g_*(T_f, q) \equiv g_*(T_f)$.

From the formula (10) it directly follows that

$$\begin{aligned} t_{f,q} &= t_f \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) < t_f, \\ H_{f,q} &= H_f \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) > H_f, \\ T_{f,q} &= T_f \exp\left(-\frac{1}{4}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) > T_f, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

i. e., when **qgcs**-corrections are taken into account, the formation time of PBH decreases, the Hubble parameter H_f and the temperature T_f are increasing. Besides, to meet the conditions $\gtrsim \frac{\gamma}{3} \text{ g}$ in (39), the initial black hole (disregarding **qgcs**-corrections) should have a larger mass.

Remark 4.1

4.1.1 Note that, due to

$$\frac{M}{t_f} = \frac{M_q}{t_{f,q}} = \frac{1}{\gamma m_p^2}, \quad (43)$$

such a property from [41] that the ratio M/t_f is independent of the BH mass is retained when **qgcs**-corrections are taken into account.

4.1.2

In [1] the formula for transformation of the Hubble parameter H in the de Sitter phase, with M_q -**deformation** of PBH having the (SdS) metric, has been derived (formula (20) in Section 2. The second line in (42) points to the fact that this formula remains valid in radiation-dominant phase as well.

As noted in [41], in our consideration the radiation mass density ρ_R can be approximated by expression in the right-hand side of the formula (44) ((4) in [41]), where it is assumed that only the particles in thermal equilibrium are considered and their mass is below temperature of the radiation bath T :

$$\rho_R = (k_B T)^4 \frac{\pi^2 g_*(T)}{30}, \quad g_*(T) = \sum_B g_B + \frac{7}{8} \sum_F g_F. \quad (44)$$

Here, similar to formula (41) but only in the general case, $g_{B(F)}$ is the number of degrees of freedom (dofs) for each boson (fermion). Obviously, the quantities $T, g_*(T), \rho_R$ are independent of the M_q -**deformation**.

4.2. Black holes accretion and evaporation

Then, making from (10) the substitution $M \rightarrow M_q, r_M \rightarrow r_{M_q}$ in the corresponding formulae, from [41] we can derive **qgcs**-corrections for the accretion rate ([41], the formula (11)):

$$\frac{dM_q}{dt} = f_{acc}(4\pi r_{M_q}^2) \rho_R, \quad (45)$$

where, in symbols of [41], $f_{acc} = O(1)$ is the accretion efficiency. According to (10), we have

$$\frac{dM_q}{dt} = f_{acc}(4\pi r_{M_q}^2) \rho_R = f_{acc}(4\pi r_M^2 \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right)) \rho_R < f_{acc}(4\pi r_{M_{BH}}^2) \rho_R = \frac{dM_{BH}}{dt}. \quad (46)$$

From this it follows that, compared with the semiclassical consideration, in the M_q -**deformed** pattern the accretion rate is lowering by a factor of $\exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) < 1$. Similar to [41] in (46), replacing ρ_R by the corresponding value from the right-hand side of (44), we can obtain formula (12) from [41] with the substitution $M \rightarrow M_q$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dM_q}{dt} &= \frac{8\pi^3}{15} f_{acc} g_*(T) \frac{M_q^2}{m_p^4} (k_B T)^4 \\ &= f_{acc} \frac{3}{2} \frac{M_q^2}{m_p^4} t^{-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Note that, since properties of the Lambert function $W(u)$ have been studied sufficiently [25], we can estimate the quantity

$\exp\left(\pm W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right)$ to a high accuracy for the particular black hole of the mass M . Moreover, from the formula (25) in [17] that is given in formula (9) of the present paper, we can easily obtain the following quantities in the form of a similar series using the undetermined coefficients method:

$$\begin{aligned} &\exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \exp\left(\pm W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \\ &\exp\left(\pm \frac{1}{4}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \dots, \end{aligned}$$

what is noted in **Remark 2.3** from [1].

On the contrary, in the M_q -**deformed** consideration, the evaporation rate increases

compared to the semi-classical picture. Indeed, replacing in the corresponding formula from [42],[43],[41] the evaporation rate, taking into account the M_q -**deformation**, we have

$$\frac{dM_q}{dt} = -f_{ev}(4\pi r_{M_q}^2) \rho_{M_q}, \quad (48)$$

where the sign "−" in the right-hand side means that the black hole mass decreases due to evaporation and f_{ev} is an efficiency factor for evaporation [41]. In accordance with formula (16) in [41] and given that the M_q -**deformation** is

$$\rho_{M_q} = \frac{\pi^2}{30} \frac{g_{M_q}(T_{M_q})}{4} (k_B T_{M_q})^4, \quad (49)$$

by substitution of the quantity ρ_{M_q} from the last formula in (48) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dM_q}{dt} &= -f_{ev}(4\pi r_{M_q}^2) \rho_{M_q} \\ &= -\frac{\pi^3}{30} \frac{f_{ev} g_{M_q}(T_{M_q})}{4} r_{M_q}^2 (k_B T_{M_q})^4 \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

In the last two formulae the quantity g_{M_q} and its semiclassical analogue g_M in [41] are defined similar to $g_*(T)$. But the distinction is that it depends on the M_q -**deformation**. Indeed, the quantity $g_M(T_M)$ is equal to the overall number of boson and fermion degrees of freedom for temperature below T_M . From the formula (9) it follows that $T_{M_q} > T_M$ and hence we have $g_{M_q}(T_{M_q}) \neq g_M(T_M)$ and in the general case $g_{M_q}(T_{M_q}) \geq g_M(T_M)$.

By substitution of the values for the M_q -**deformed** quantities from the formulae (9) and (10) in (50), due to the fact that $\exp(-W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M})) > 1$ and $g_{M_q}(T_{M_q}) \geq g_M(T_M)$, we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dM_q}{dt} &= -\frac{\pi^3}{30} \frac{f_{ev} g_{M_q}(T_{M_q})}{4} r_{M_q}^2 (k_B T_{M_q})^4 \\ &= -\frac{\pi^3}{30} \frac{f_{ev} g_{M_q}(T_M)}{4} r_M^2 (k_B T_M)^4 \cdot \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \leq \frac{dM}{dt} \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) < \frac{dM}{dt}. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

The last inequality in (51) is associated with the fact that $\exp(-W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M})) > 1$ and the quantity dM/dt is negative because the BH mass M decreases in the process of evaporation. Thus, in the M_q -**deformed** pattern the black hole

evaporation process is intensified.

As in the case of high-mass black holes, i. e. black holes with the mass $M \gg M_0$, for the quantity $M_0/M \approx 0$ and consequently for all the quantities we have

$$\exp\left(\pm \frac{1}{2} W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right), \exp\left(\pm W\left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right), \dots \approx 1,$$

and hence, to a high accuracy, we have $T_{M_q} \approx T_M, g_{M_q} \approx g_M$. Then the conclusions from

[41] are valid for black holes as is supported

by comparison of the formulae (47) and (50). However, we should take into consideration that a PBH loses its mass in the process of evaporation to become eventually the black hole with the mass $M_{Evap,q} \simeq M_0$, where we have $M_{Evap,q}$ from formula (37). In this case only the quantities with the subscript "q" are correct.

Remark 4.2

Since, for large black holes with the mass $M \gg M_0$, the M_q -**deformed** quantities are almost indistinguishable from the corresponding quantities in a semiclassical approximation, the Remark from Section 3.3 in [41] is valid for them: *If the temperature T of the radiation bath is higher than the BH temperature, i.e., $T > T_M$, accretion dominates over evaporation, otherwise it is negligible.*

If, similar to [41], time is denoted as t_{acc} when radiation temperature equals the BH temperature, for $M \gg M_0$ we always have $t_{acc} \gg t_f$, and if the final mass of a PBH at the moment of accretion termination (condition $T = T_M$) is denoted as M^{acc} , of importance is a value of the relative mass increase ([41], formula (18))

$$R_{acc} \equiv \frac{M^{acc}}{M}. \quad (52)$$

The numerator in the right-hand side of the last expression is equal to the summed values of M with the time integral at the length $[t_f, t_{T=T_M}]$ from the right side of formula (13) in [41]:

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = f_{acc} \frac{3}{2} \frac{M^2}{m_p^2} t^{-1}, \quad (53)$$

taking the form (47) in the M_q -**deformation** pattern.

Considering the two formulae, with regard to M_q -**deformation** we have

$$R_{acc,q} = \frac{M^{acc,q}}{M_q} = \frac{M_q + \int_t^{t_{T=T_M}} f_{acc} \frac{3}{2} \frac{M_q^2}{m_p^2} t^{-1}}{M_q}. \quad (54)$$

It is clear that **Remark 4.2** is unapplicable to a BH with small mass $M_q \simeq M_0$ (denoted in this paper as **pqbh**) because from the start

we have $T_{M_q} \propto T_p$ (where T_p is the Planck temperature) and hence $T_{M_q} \gg T$. In this case evaporation dominates over accretion, **pqbh** is rapidly evaporating, though not completely, as, due to **GUP** in Section 2, evaporation of a BH is always incomplete and it has the Planckian remnant.

Remark 4.3

Note that from Section 2 we have $M \approx M_q, r_M \approx r_{M_q}$ for large black holes. This means that in the exponential small-parameter α_{r_M} expansion the greatest contribution is made by the leading term, contributions of all other terms being insignificant. The accretion process enhances this property because in this case the black hole mass is growing. At the same time, in the process of evaporation the BH mass decreases. In the corresponding exponents the terms containing $\alpha_{r_M}^n, n \geq 1$, where n -integer, begin to play a significant part. The greater mass loss has a black hole during this process, the greater is the number n , for which we should take into account the terms containing $\alpha_{r_M}^{\tilde{n}}, \tilde{n} \leq n$ in the relevant expansion. For quantum **pbhs**, we should from the start take into account the terms containing $\alpha_{r_M}^n, n \geq 1$ in the exponential expansion in terms of α_{r_M} . . Evaporation processes lead to an increase in \tilde{n} . Only in the case of rather great accretion we could have $n = 0$ to a high accuracy.

Remark 4.4

We have used the notation from [41]. Still, as follows from Section 2 of the present paper, it is more convenient to use in calculations the horizon event radius r_{M_q} instead of the black hole deformed mass M_q . Then some formulae, specifically (46) and (48), automatically turn to the ordinary differential equations for r_{M_q} .

5. Final comments and further research

This paper is a continuation of the study into the quantum-gravity corrections for **pbhs**, based on the validity of **GUP** (6), that was initiated by the publications [1]–[4].

5.1 In Section 3 the proposed methods have been used for solving the dark energy problem in the case when this energy presents the cosmological vacuum energy, with the density identical to the cosmological term Λ accurate to the known constants. But we should remember the importance of the dark energy model constructed on the *quintessence* that is a canonical scalar field ϕ with the pressure and the energy density given, respectively, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi &= \dot{\phi}^2/2 - V(\phi), \\ \rho_\phi &= \dot{\phi}^2/2 + V(\phi), \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

the dark energy equation of state is

$$w \equiv \frac{P_\phi}{\rho_\phi} = \frac{\dot{\phi}^2/2 - V(\phi)}{\dot{\phi}^2/2 + V(\phi)}. \quad (56)$$

and ϕ satisfies the continuity equation

$$(\dot{\rho}_\phi + 3H(\rho_\phi + P_\phi) = 0) \equiv (\ddot{\phi} + 3H\dot{\phi} + V_{,\phi} = 0). \quad (57)$$

Here as usually $V_{,\phi} \equiv dV/d\phi$.

As the Hubble parameter H is varying in the case of the M_q -**deformation**(formulae (20),(42), other quantities in (55)–(57), specifically, the *quintessence* ϕ , are also transformed by the M_q -**deformation**. A study of the M_q -**deformation** dark energy model based on the *quintessence* ϕ seems to be a separate problem.

5.2 In Section 4 the accretion and evaporation processes during the radiation dominant era have been studied within the scope of M_q -**deformation**. It is essential to apply the obtained results to other processes in the Universe, in particular to the formation of dark energy [41]. It is important that, as evaporation of **pbhs** is not complete in this pattern (formula (8)), the retained Planckian remnant may be a part of the dark matter [19].

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